

“Damages And Repair System Of Protein And Nucleic Acids: A Short Review”

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Abstract: Cellular wear and tear leads to macromolecular damages in many forms. Efficient repair of such damages needs enzyme system and accessory protein. Enzymes targeting nucleic acids and bases play important role in repair of DNA backbone where as protein repairing enzymes like PIMT, MsrA, PPIases and Trx maintains the protein chain. Any deviation to this may lead to alteration in macromolecular structure and function which ultimately compromises cellular survival and metabolic fate. In this review, few of such mechanisms have been discussed.

(Key words: Protein repairing enzymes, PIMT, Trx)

1. Introduction:

Macromolecules like carbohydrate, lipid, protein, nucleic acid forms the basis of cellular structure and function. Out of these complex biochemical elements, nucleic acids and proteins play major role in the flow of information. The central dogma of information starts from DNA, gets transcribed into RNA and results into protein, the 'executor'. The ubiquitous phenomenon of wear and tear is also applied to these elements during the process of metabolic turnover of cells. Also, various stress conditions induce structural as well as functional changes in these macromolecules. Whenever any living cell (like eukaryotic or prokaryotic) confronts these damages, it has got two options to deal with it.

1. To replace the altered macromolecules (which is an energy consuming process)
2. To repair them

2. Repair: The most opted approach for nucleic acid repair

Clearly, many times, a cell will go for the second option, i. e. repair to conserve its energy. Extensive research in genomics and proteomics has provided a fair insight into the damage and repair system of nucleic acids and proteins. The knowledge of such pathways has provided a new platform in the field of prevention of various infectious diseases. DNA, the store house of information confronts various damages in various conditions. Such as UV mediated damages like formation of cyclobutane pyrimidine dimers (CPD),

pyrimidine pyrimidone photoproducts (6-4PP) (Goosen and Moolenaar, 2008). Apart from UV mediated damages, conformational and covalent modifications also elicited by heat, oxidative reagents, change in pH (Viscik and Clarke, 1995). DNA is also subjected to depurination or deamination through spontaneous chemical reactions (Kushner, 1987). Many of the above-mentioned damages are also common to RNA. In cell various mechanisms of DNA repair exists, most of them are mediated via enzymes. These mechanisms include direct reversal of damages by photolyases (photoreactivation), repair of the damaged base by DNA glycosylase (base excision repair), incision of the DNA adjacent to the damage by endonucleases (UV damage endonucleases), removal of complete oligonucleotide containing the damage (nucleotide excision repair) (Goosen and Moolenaar, 2008). One of the important groups of damaging agents are endogenous (i. e. S-adenosyl methionine) and environmental alkylating agents (i. e. Chloromethane and other halocarbons) (Drablos *et al.*, 2004). Alkylating agents cause alkylation of the majority of N- and O- atoms in DNA and RNA bases. Bacterial and mammalian AlkB proteins (Fe₂₊) and 2-oxo-glutarate dependent dioxygenase can reverse methylation damages. The *E. coli* protein AlkB was recently shown to be an oxidative DNA methylase that repairs the cytotoxic lesions like 1-meA and 3-meC in DNA (Drablos *et al.*, 2004).

3. Execution of the executor: the protein chapter

Like DNA, proteins are also subjected to various forms of damages that can render them nonfunctional. According to physiological regulation of cell, various proteins undergo spontaneous conformational and covalent modifications. But the rates of these reactions increased by environmental/ other stresses such as heat, oxidative changes or changes in pH and osmotic conditions (Viscik and Clarke, 1995).

Protein damages can be classified generally into two different categories.

- a. Conformational damage or alteration of the three-dimensional structure of the protein without changing its chemical makeup.
- b. Covalent modification of the amino acids (Viscik and Clarke, 1995).

Bacteria deals with these damages mostly by 3 different mechanisms

- I. Chaperones play an important role in *de novo* folding of newly synthesized proteins. Apart from that they also take care of conformationally distorted proteins.
- II. Enzymatic system exists, which can repair covalently modified amino acids. For example isomerized prolines, oxidized methionine and iso-Asp can be repaired enzymatically.
- III. When these two above mentioned mechanisms unable to repair the damaged protein the cell takes necessary steps to eliminate it.

4. Role of chaperone in protein refolding

All the information required for protein folding resides on its amino acid sequence (Anfinsen, 1973). Despite of their correct initial folding, there is always some tendency for proteins to subsequently unfold or aggregate. It is now clear that GroEL and DnaK help to maintain the functional conformations of existing proteins. Their ability to bind unfolded polypeptides and facilitate renaturation has been demonstrated both *in vitro* and *in vivo* (Kawata *et al.*, 1994) Increased production of chaperones is common to nearly all known stress responses. Heat, ethanol, nutrient limitation, oxidizing agents, high or low pH, nalidixic acid, UV irradiation, puromycin, phage infection and alkylating agents are all factors that induce GroEL and DnaK synthesis

(Neidhardt and VanBogelen, 1987) Similarly the quaternary, tertiary or secondary structure of proteins can be disturbed by many factors, including heat, cold, salts, acid or alkaline pH, high osmotic pressure, alcohol and oxidizing agents, both *in vitro* (Davies and Delsignore, 1987) and *in vivo* Apart from these, Hsp 33 and Prohibitin are two new world chaperones found to be important in protein modification process.

5. Covalent damages of protein need specific enzymes for their repair

Covalent modifications of amino acids lead in altered proteins in cell which has to be repair for cellular survival. One of these kinds of change is formation of disulfide bonds in proteins under oxidizing environment. Protein disulfide isomerase, which catalyses this process, is an important member of the protein-folding pathway (Freedman, 1989). In *E. coli* the periplasmic proteins DsbA and DsbC catalyzes isomerization of disulfide bonds needed for activity of periplasmic and outer-membrane proteins. Another good example will be proline isomerization and its repair. In proline, peptide bonds can exist in either the 'normal' trans-configuration or in the cis-form (Fischer et al., 1983). The presence of the inappropriate cis-isomers can greatly retard protein folding or refolding (Lang et al., 1987) which results in compromised function and importantly impaired degradation and removal from the cell. Peptidyl-prolyl cis-trans isomerases catalyse proline isomerization, have been identified in many organisms and shown to increase the rate of protein folding. *E. coli* has genes for at least three such isomerases as ppiA and ppiB, which encode periplasmic and cytoplasmic enzymes, respectively (Hayano et al., 1991), and ppiC, encoding a new protein of unknown localization. Oxidizing agents contribute a major part of covalent modification. Hydroxyl (OH-), hydroperoxyl (HOO-), superoxide (O₂-) or lipid peroxy radicals are the major oxidants generated in the biological system. These oxidizing agents mostly target amino acids like methionine, cysteine, tyrosine, histidine and tryptophan. Methionine sulfoxide reductase recognizes methionine sulfoxide as an abnormal amino acid and can reduce it back to methionine, using reduced thioredoxin as a substrate. L-isoaspartyl protein carboxyl methyltransferase specifically binds L-iso aspartyl residues in proteins (Mishra and Mahawar, 2019) and methylates the side-chain carboxyl group using S-adenosyl methionine (SAM) as a methyl donor thus helps in isoaspartate repair. This particular enzyme has been found to be distributed in various bacteria (Li and Clarke, 1992) suggesting role of this enzyme in cellular survival under various stress conditions. MsrA and PIMT play important roles in repair of covalent damages in protein (Dixit *et al.*, 2017). Mutant strains of *msr* gene of *Mycobacterium smegmatis* (Douglas et al., 2004), *Staphylococcus aureus*, *E. coli*, *Helicobacter pylori* and *Neisseria gonorrhoea* were found to be hypersensitive to oxidative stress. Mishra et. al (2020) showed that PIMT in *Salmonella Typhimurium* interacts with 6 different targets which are essential for its survival and pathogenicity.

Conclusion:

Damage to cellular macromolecules is a natural and normal process. But failure to repair any such kind of repair may lead to blockage, inhibition and regulation of many key intermediary processes which may derail the normal cellular functionalities and may severely affect its ultimate output and coordination. The mentioned enzymes and restoring systems actively participate in ensuring its normal mode of action. Though few of the enzymes and associated systems have been reported but involvement of many others is yet to be explored.

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